

Preparation of Some Optically Active Dianilides of L-(+)-Glutamic Acid

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Several optically active dianilides of the type:

have been prepared by condensation of simple as well as mono- and di-substituted anilines, with L-(+)-glutamic acid¹. L-(+)-Glutamic acid racemises on prolonged heating² at 160-70° in water. In our experiments with the reactions even at high temperature and on prolonged heating, the optical activity is retained and the resultant dianilides are optically active. These also do not show colour reactions with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde³. Optical rotations of the dianilides with R having *o*-, *m*-, and *p*- substituted anilines have been determined in solvents like chloroform, acetone, ethyl acetate, methyl acetate, and dioxane in the following order: *o*- > *m*- > *p*-. In methanol and ethanol, these, however, show irregularity in rotations. Optically active dianilides and their rotations are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Dianilides of the type R. CO.NH.CH(NH₂).CH₂.CH₂.CO.NH.R.

No.	Glutamic dianilides. (R =).	Formula.	M.P.	[α] _D ²⁵ (l, l.) (in acetone).	Found.	Reqd.
1	Aniline	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	198°	-14.61	N : 14.82%	14.14%
2	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₃	156°	-36.38	N : 12.34	12.90
3	<i>p</i> - "	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₃	206°	-14.50	N : 12.62	12.90
4	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₃	95°	-32.72	N : 11.38	11.76
5	<i>m</i> - "	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₃	152°	-17.69	N : 11.40	11.76
6	<i>p</i> - "	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₃	203°	-12.97	N : 11.43	11.76
7	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	194°	-26.28	Cl : 19.04	19.18
8	<i>m</i> - "	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	80°	-13.80	Cl : 18.74	19.18
9	<i>p</i> - "	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	203°	-11.39	Cl : 18.74	19.18
10	<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₃	133°	-34.22	N : 10.68	10.90
11	<i>p</i> - "	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₃	195°	-21.63	N : 10.52	10.90
12	2,3-Dichloroaniline	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₄	203°	-16.79	Cl : 32.08	32.32
13	3,4- "	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₄	190°	-14.79	Cl : 32.00	32.32
14	2,4- "	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₄	169°	-26.31	Cl : 31.58	32.32
15	2,5- "	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₄	177°	-19.75	Cl : 32.02	32.32

1. Hageunen, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Biol.*, 1924, 6, 673.

2. Jeannerat, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1942, 9, 637.

3. Gray, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1922, 1264.

TABLE II

Optical rotations of the active di-anilides in various solvents.

*No.	[α] _D ²⁵ (c, 2.5; l, 1) in						
	CHCl ₃ .	Acetone.	EtAc.	MeAc.	Dioxane.	MeOH.	EtOH.
1.	-29.17°	-14.61°	-27.28°	-25.75	-14.21°	16.80°	+12.850°
2.	-53.02°	-36.38°	-43.92°	-31.43°	-24.57°	7.800°	+ 3.796°
3.	-28.57°	-14.50°	..	-13.95°	-12.95°	17.310°	+ 12.500°
4.	-50.30°	-35.72°	-40.86°	-30.86°	-23.17°	..	+ 8.690°
5.	-33.30°	-17.69°	-30.31°	-15.07°	-11.16°	4.854°	+ 9.550°
6.	-23.42°	-12.97°	..	-12.50°	-4.027°	5.442°	+ 10.740°
7.	-45.32°	-26.28°	-34.44°	..	-13.37°	..	..
8.	-22.04°	-13.80°	-21.06°	-14.68°	-10.53°	6.443°	+ 7.194°
9.	..	-11.39°	-16.25°	-12.54°	- 1.416°	15.250°	+ 16.520°
10.	-48.04°	-34.22°	-40.70°	-30.12°	-20.50°	-9.842°	- 13.040°
11.	-38.84°	-21.63°	-37.02°	-23.81°	-17.19°	5.264°	..
12.	-25.87°	-16.79°	-22.04°	-23.13°	- 7.78°	-1.010°	- 9.480°
13.	..	-14.79°	-21.21°	-21.49°	- 6.58°	23.180°	+ 4.620°
14.	-47.37°	-26.31°	-28.74°	-36.67°	-10.67°	..	- 4.260°
15.	-36.77°	-19.75°	-22.86°	-24.60°	- 8.62°	..	..

*The number refers to glutamic dianilides of R as in Table I.

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